

This is a pre-print version. This paper has been published in: Fairhurst, Jordi (2022). "The Early Wittgenstein on Living a Good Ethical Life." Philosophia, 50 (4):1745-1767. See: doi.org/10.1007/s11406-022-00485-0. Please only cite the published version.

The early Wittgenstein on living a good ethical life

Abstract

This paper offers a novel interpretation of Wittgenstein's early conception of ethics and the good ethical life. Initially, it critically examines the widespread view according to which Wittgenstein's early conception of ethics and the good ethical life involves having a certain ethical attitude to the world. It points out that this reading incurs in some mistakes and shortcomings, thereby suggesting the need for an alternative reading that avoids and amends these inadequacies. Subsequently, it sets out to offer said reading. Specifically, it is argued that the good ethical life is predicated on a good exercise of the ethical will and solving the riddle of life, both of which demand a certain view of, and not an attitude to, the world. This view is the view of the world *sub specie aeterni*.

Key Words

Wittgenstein; Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus; Ethics; Good ethical life; Ethical will; Meaning of life.

Introduction

For early Wittgenstein's philosophy, ethics undoubtedly played a central role in the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* (hereafter, *Tractatus*). He went as far as stating, in a letter to Von Ficker, that the point of the book is ethical. Despite the overarching importance of ethics, Wittgenstein left us with a small handful of obscure and cryptic propositions about ethics at the end of the *Tractatus*. These propositions have proven extremely hard to interpret, as evidenced by the multiple ongoing exegetical discussions among Wittgenstein scholars.

In this paper I attempt to shed some light on Wittgenstein's early conception of ethics and the good ethical life in the *Tractatus*. I begin, in section 1, by outlining Wittgenstein's characterization of ethical value and spelling out its consequences for ethics. Subsequently, in section 2, I examine the widespread view according to which

Wittgenstein's early conception of ethics and the good ethical life involves having a certain ethical attitude to the world. Finally, in the last sections, I set out to provide a novel interpretation by examining Wittgenstein's understanding of the ethical will and the riddle of life in the *Tractatus*.

1. Ethics in the *Tractatus*

In propositions 6.4 and 6.41 Wittgenstein explains that ethical value *must* lie outside the world. This is due to the incompatible characterization he offers of the world and ethical value (cf. [TLP: 6.4-6.422, 6.4321]). The world is composed of accidental facts: it is the sphere of what happens and is the case. Meanwhile, ethical value is non-accidental: it is the sphere of what is absolutely and necessarily valuable. If ethical value existed in the world it would itself be accidental and, thereby, be of no value.

Wittgenstein, consequently, endorses the fact-value distinction, which he had earlier defended in the *Notebooks* (cf. [NB: 5.7.16, 2.8.16, 12.10.16]) and later re-asserted in 'Lecture on ethics' (cf. [LOE: 5-7, 10]) when distinguishing between judgments of *relative* value (i.e., statements of facts) and judgments of *absolute* (ethical) value. Accidental facts cannot inherently possess ethical value: they are neither ethically good nor ethically bad.

It may be argued that facts can still be extrinsically good, despite not being intrinsically good. For instance, they may be good for a certain purpose or because they stand in some relation to something. Wittgenstein, unfortunately, also rejects this idea. He explains that ethical goodness is universal and necessary, not relative to accidental and contingent ends which are dependent on personal inclinations [LOE: 5-7]. Ethical goodness is 'the absolute right road': "the road which everybody on seeing it would, with logical necessity, have to go, or be ashamed for not going" [LOE: 7]. The necessity and universality that characterizes ethical goodness (and absolute ethical value in general) cannot be found in, or related to, accidental and contingent facts in the world.

If absolute goodness were intrinsically or extrinsically related to a fact, it 'would be one which everybody, independent of his tastes and inclinations, would necessarily bring about or feel guilty for not bringing about. And I want to say that such a state of affairs is a chimera' [LOE: 7]. Facts are neither intrinsically nor extrinsically valuable, they do not belong to the solution of ethical problems [TLP, 6.4321]. This is exemplified by Wittgenstein's critique of the famous quote from Hamlet: 'Nothing is either good or bad, but thinking makes it so', i.e., things are extrinsically good or bad, not intrinsically

good or bad. Against Hamlet, Wittgenstein argues that ‘a state of mind, so far as we mean by that a fact which we can describe, is in no ethical sense good or bad’ [LOE: 6]. Moreover, Wittgenstein went as far as stating that a murder is on the same level as any other event in the world (e.g., the falling of a stone) in order to emphasize the severity of the fact-value distinction [NB: 12.10.16; LOE: 6-7].

This does not mean that facts are ethically *irrelevant*. They can contribute to setting ethical problems [TLP: 6.4321]. However, they cannot contribute to their solution. The objective mark of ethical goodness and a good ethical life cannot be something described in senseful propositions. ‘This mark cannot be a physical one but only a metaphysical one, a transcendental one’ [NB, 30.7.16].

Wittgenstein’s fact-value distinction means ‘there can be no ethical propositions’ [TLP: 6.42]. According to Wittgenstein, there are two conditions for the sense of pictures (i.e., thoughts and propositions). First, they must be logical pictures. Namely, they must share their logical form with the reality they depict [TLP: 2.181-2.19, 3, 4.03]. Second, they must depict (or represent) the existence and non-existence of states of affairs [TLP: 2.221-2.222, 4.01, 4.023, 4.1, 4.2]. Given that ethical value *must* lie outside of the world, there are no ethical states of affairs to be represented. Thus, there are no senseful or meaningful ethical propositions. ‘Propositions can express nothing that is higher’ ([TLP: 6.42] cf. [NB: 30.7.16; LOE: 7]).

Wittgenstein remarks in 6.4-6.422 have generally been interpreted as involving a rejection of traditional philosophical ethics. Namely, Wittgenstein, in the *Tractatus*, does not intend to outline a philosophical ethical theory that, through the use of ethical propositions, provides an ethical doctrine with certain imperatives or ethical laws that regulate our behaviour and specify what is right and wrong conduct.¹ When faced by an ethical law of the form ‘Thou shalt...’ one can simply contend ‘And what if I do not do it’ [TLP 6.422] (cf. [NB: 30.7.16; LOE: 7, 10; Waismann 1979: 117-118; CV: 4/MS 107 192 c: 10.11.1929]). The rejection of traditional philosophical ethics coincides with Wittgenstein’s rejection of philosophical and metaphysical theories (cf. [TLP: 3.324,

¹ Wittgenstein, in his meetings with the Vienna Circle between 1929-1931, stated: ‘if I could explain the essence of the ethical only by means of a theory, then what is ethical would be of no value whatsoever. [...] For me a theory is without value. A theory gives me nothing’ [Waismann 1979: 117]. Morris [2008, 326] fails to acknowledge these remarks and (mis)interprets Wittgenstein as advancing a particular kind of normative ethics with ethical imperatives.

4.112, 6.53; NB: 2.12.16]). However, given that Wittgenstein discards traditional ethical theories, what is the *Tractarian* ethics about?

Following his initial characterization of ethics, Wittgenstein [TLP 6.422] explains that ethics has to do with *ethical punishment*, which must be something unpleasant, and *ethical reward*, which must be something pleasant. These terms are not to be understood in their usual sense, i.e., as certain happenings in the world that are *consequences* of our actions. Conversely, ethical reward and ethical punishment ‘must reside in the action itself’ [TLP: 6.422] and are later identified as ethical happiness and ethical unhappiness respectively (cf. [TLP: 6.422, 6.43]).

Ethics, then, is concerned with being ethically good, receiving ethical reward (i.e., happiness) and living a good ethical life (cf. [TLP: 6.422-6.45]). However, given Wittgenstein’s fact-value distinction, being ethically good and acting correctly are not to be identified with certain facts or happenings in the world. Namely, the mark of ethical goodness and ethical badness *cannot* be a physical mark, as it would be of no value [TLP: 6.41] (cf. [NB 30.7.16]). This raises some interesting and puzzling questions: how should ethical actions be understood? What is the mark of ethical goodness and ethical badness? And, finally, what is needed for a good ethical life?

2. An attitude to the world

According to a widespread reading, being ethically good and living a good ethical life involve having a certain ethical attitude to the world. Wittgenstein scholars have mainly characterized this ethical attitude in two different ways.² First, Cavalier [1980: 159-160, 165-166, 173-175, 187-195], Worthington [1981: 486-489], Edwards [1982, 26, 46-47, 57, 67-68], Thomas [1999: 196], Diamond [2000: 153-155], Churchill [2009: 113-114, 121-123], Hughes [2009: 52, 56-58], Appelqvist [2013: 47-49, 51, 53] and Kuusela [2018: 45-51] hold that the correct ethical attitude is living in acceptance or agreement with the facts of the world, whatever they may be.

² This section critically examines some inadequate aspects common to some existing proposals via short characterizations that bring out the problematic features they share. Thus, my brief characterizations do not flesh out the subtleties of these proposals, which are far too intricate as to discuss in detail here. My aim here, however, is not to discuss all the intricacies of these proposals, but rather draw attention to certain shortcomings that need to be amended. Accordingly, the criticisms I will offer do not undermine the entirety of the proposals I discuss. Furthermore, in section 3 I resort to some of their ideas to develop my own proposal.

Hughes, Appelqvist and Churchill add that this acceptance is the result of “doing the will of God”, i.e., living “in agreement with that alien will, on which I am dependent” (NB, 8.7.16). (Kuusela [2018, 46] also quotes this entry of the Notebooks, but suggests that it is no more than a simile). Appelqvist and Hughes, together with Thomas, further suggest that we can only live in acceptance with the world “-and so in a certain sense master it- by renouncing any influence on happenings” [NB, 11.6.16]. This renunciation entails a submission to the will or (power) of God. Kuusela, in turn, is critical of this renunciation. He explains that renouncing influence on the world “is morally questionable insofar as it may lead, for example, to a passive acceptance of injustices” ([Kuusela 2018: 49] see note 15). Instead, ethics is concerned with “a particular mode of our experience of the world [...] as valuable and meaningful” [Kuusela 2018, 47]. This experience is that of living in harmony with reality by adopting the attitude that, whatever one wills, the outcome must be accepted.

Second, Rudebush and Berg [1979: 152-153], Mulhall [2007: 232-233, 236, 243-245], Tejedor [2013: 63, 73-79] and Harchourt [Forthcoming: 1-5, 8-9] explain that the correct ethical attitude amounts to having conceptual clarity. The successful application of Wittgenstein’s philosophical method, namely the correct method in philosophy described in 6.53, results in achieving conceptual clarity and, therefore, being ethically good and living a good ethical life.

Tejedor [2013, 74-74] holds that having a religious or ethical attitude to the world involves being in a state of conceptual clarity. Namely, it is being clear about certain formal concepts, having certain practical abilities honed in and thus being disposed to use things so as to reflect the fundamental contingency of facts. This, in turn, involves treating ourselves (i.e., human beings) as facts on a par, with respect to their contingency, with all other facts in the world [Tejedor 2013, 74]. On this interpretation, the *Tractatus* has an ethical purpose, not because it contains the TLP 6.4ff, “but because the book -as a whole- enables us to hone in our mastery of certain formal concepts” ([Tejedor 2013, 78]; for a study on the ethical point of the *Tractatus* see Fairhurst [2021]).

Mulhall [2007, 45] explains that the “successful application of this philosophical method will constitute an expression of the orientation of the happy person – a capacity to accept the world and its limits, to overcome any apprehension of oneself as limited, constrained or punished thereby”. By contrast, anyone who runs up against the limits of language and, by extension, the world is an inhabitant of the world of the unhappy because they experience everything that happens as an imposition. Like Tejedor, on this

interpretation the *Tractatus* has an ethical purpose, not because it contains the TLP 6.4ff, but because the whole book makes manifest the attitude of the happy person. Furthermore, this ethical point may be contained in “any form of writing that makes manifest the attitude or orientation of the happy person” [Mulhall 2007, 245].

Finally, Harcourt argues that philosophical confusion is a mark of personal badness and that only the correct method of philosophy remedies this confusion. “It follows that philosophy, when practiced successfully,” results in conceptual clarity and thus “makes one better” [Harcourt Forthcoming, 1]. Relatedly, Rudebush and Berg [1979, 153] suggest that Wittgenstein saw the correct method of philosophy as a machine that allowed him to overcome his lack of decency.

There are two pressing issues that affect defendants of this widespread reading – even those interpreters (e.g. [Kelly 1995: 575]) who claim that Wittgenstein does not detail what this ethical attitude is. On the one hand, there is no evidence in the *Tractatus* to support the claim that being ethically good and living a good ethical life involves having a certain ethical attitude to the world. This widespread reading originated from Wittgenstein’s *Notebooks*, where he claims that ‘the will is an attitude of the subject to the world’ [NB: 4.11.16]. Interpreters (implicitly or explicitly) used this remark to characterize the ethical will in 6.423-6.43 of the *Tractatus* and, by extension, Wittgenstein’s ethics.

In 4.11.16 Wittgenstein engages in a thoughtful discussion about the will –a topic he had become highly interested in during 1916. Throughout the entry he studies the connection between our will and the actions that constitute its fulfilment, the differences between wishing and willing and so on. Leaving aside the intricacies of this entry, it is important to take note that Wittgenstein is studying the will as a *phenomenon* in the world, as evidenced by the following passages:

It is clear, so to speak, that we need a foothold for the will in the world.

[...]

The act of the will is not the cause of the action but is the action itself.

[...]

If the will has to have an object in the world, the object can be the intended action itself.

And the will does have to have an object.

Otherwise we should have no foothold and could not know what we willed.

And could not will different things.

[...]

My will fastens on to the world somewhere, and does not fasten on to other things. [NB: 4.11.16]

As Wittgenstein later explains in 6.423 of the *Tractatus*, the will as a *phenomenon* is of interest only to psychology. Ethics, meanwhile, is interested in a different will: the will as the subject of the ethical, i.e., the ethical will.³ This ethical will, given Wittgenstein's fact-value distinction, cannot have a foothold or object in the world: it does not fasten onto certain things or happenings in the world. In other words, the *ethical* will is not the *phenomenal* will.

It is misguided, therefore, to resort to 4.11.16 in order to offer an interpretation of the ethical will in the *Tractatus* and suggest that ethics is primarily concerned with having a certain attitude to the world. Wittgenstein focuses solely on the phenomenal will in 4.11.16. He shows no interest in ethical issues and refrains from revisiting his earlier ethical discussions surrounding the will. The characterization of the *phenomenal* will as a certain attitude does not contribute to, nor deepen, our understanding of the ethical will in 6.423 nor his ethics in the *Tractatus*. Furthermore, there is no evidence to determine whether Wittgenstein still conceived the *phenomenal* will as an attitude in the *Tractatus* or if he had abandoned this idea at some point after 1916.

On the other hand, some defendants (e.g. [Rudebush and Berg 1979: 152; Cavalier 1980: 159-160, 165-166, 173-175, 187-195; Edwards 1982: 26, 46-47, 57, 67-68; Mulhall 2007: 232-234; Tejedor 2013: 73-79; Harchourt Forthcoming: 1-5]) of this widespread reading implicitly or explicitly conceive the correct ethical attitude as a mental state or state of mind. For instance, Rudebush and Berg, Mulhall, Tejedor and Harchourt argue that the correct ethical attitude is conceptual clarity, a state of mind which is manifested in our disposition to use signs correctly.⁴ (Other interpreters (e.g., [Hughes 2008: 57-58;

³ Wittgenstein did not explicitly draw this distinction in his *Notebooks*, albeit I believe that there are certain entries where he does hint towards it and implicitly assumes it (e.g. [NB 5.7.16, 21.7.16, 29.7.16, 5.8.16]). The lack of an explicit formulation of this distinction, however, comes as no surprise given that at various points Wittgenstein (e.g. [NB 8.7.16]) admits that he is unclear about the topic of the will and that he is 'still making crude mistakes! No doubt of that!' [NB 29.7.16].

⁴ Tejedor [2013, 75] attempts to avoid the claim that an ethical attitude is a mental fact by arguing that it is not an emotive response, but a disposition to use signs correctly (i.e., conceptual clarity). Although she rightfully demonstrates that dispositions are not emotive responses, I fail to see why dispositions cannot be

Chruchill 2011: 121; Appelqvist 2013: 48; Kuusela 2018: 49-50]) remain ambiguous on this topic. They often seem to assume that the correct ethical attitude is a mental state or an experience, while simultaneously repudiating this claim.)

Wittgenstein explains that ‘A state of mind, so far as we mean by that a fact which we can describe, is in no ethical sense good or bad’ [LOE: 6]. Thus, against Wittgenstein’s fact-value distinction, it is a mistake to claim that the mark of the ethical is a *physical* mark, i.e., a certain mental state [TLP: 6.41] (cf. [NB 30.7.16]). Attitudes, so far as they are facts that can be described, cannot be the mark of the ethical.

3. Viewing the world *sub specie aeterni*

The shortcomings of this interpretation suggest the need of a new interpretation of Wittgenstein’s early conception of the good ethical life. My aim henceforth is to offer this novel interpretation by arguing that the good ethical life demands a certain view of the world, instead of a certain attitude.⁵

The notions ‘seeing’ and ‘viewing’ figure among Wittgenstein’s preferred terminology when discussing ethics –he had already favoured these notions over that of ‘attitude’ in the *Notebooks* (e.g. [NB: 11.6.16, 29.7.16, 4.8.16, 5.8.16, 7.10.16, 20.10.16]). For instance, in 6.4311, he reintroduces the analogy of the visual field he had discussed when examining the metaphysical subject, which is a limit of the world –not a part of it [TLP: 5.632-5.641]. Other examples of his use of the notions ‘seeing’ and ‘viewing’ can be found in 6.45 when speaking on the view *sub specie aeterni*, in 6.521 when discussing

mental facts. A disposition is a condition or state that provides the possibility for some further specific state or behavior. Given that conceptual clarity may be understood as a describable mental state, a disposition to use signs correctly may be a dispositional mental state which is exhibited in our linguistic behavior and thoughts. A disposition to use signs in a certain way is just another describable fact in the world.

⁵ John [1988: 498-508] and Cahill [2011: 42-45, 54-58] provide a possible alternative reading which claims that the living a good ethical life requires reawakening a sense of wonder. The main issue with their proposal is that Wittgenstein neither speaks about a sense of wonder nor uses the notion ‘wonder’ in *Notebooks*, *Prototractatus* or *Tractatus*. Furthermore, the textual evidence adduced by John and Cahill is self-defeating. They primarily resort to Wittgenstein’s ‘Lecture on Ethics’, where he speaks about the experience of wonderment at the existence of the world. Wittgenstein [LOE: 10] acknowledges that this experience must surely be a fact: it takes place then and there, lasts a certain definite time and consequently is describable. ‘It is the paradox that an experience, a fact, should seem to have supernatural value’ [LOE: 10].

the solution of the problem of life and, finally, in 6.522 when examining the mystical.⁶ I believe Wittgenstein's preference for these notions is not merely arbitrary and accidental, but indicative of his conception of ethics and the good ethical life.

Between 1914-1916 Wittgenstein wrote a series of coded remarks on the left-hand pages of his wartime diaries known as *Geheime Tagebücher* –leaving the right-hand pages for his philosophical reflections known as the *Notebooks*. Interestingly, on the 6th of May 1916, he wrote: 'In constant danger of my life. . . . From time to time I despair. This is the fault of a wrong view of life' ([MS 103-09v]; Klagge's [2011: 10] translation. He spoke about the importance of viewing life correctly again on the 7th of May 1916 (cf. [MS 103-10v]) and then equated sin with a false or incorrect view of life on the 29th of July [GT: 74; MS 103-19v] –the same day he enquires about the nature of seeing in NB 29.7.16.

Both entries suggest that living a good ethical life is not accomplished through acting in a certain way or having a certain attitude. Conversely, we must learn to see and view the world and life correctly, only then we will achieve happiness and avoid sin. This idea made its way into the *Notebooks* in 7.10.16, where Wittgenstein explains that ethics and aesthetics entails seeing the world *sub specie aeterni*. He would later emphasize the ethical importance of having a correct ethical view of the world in the 6.4s of *Tractatus* when discussing the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* and its role in ethics and the good ethical life.

Wittgenstein's conception of the good ethical life in the 6.4s is predicated around a good exercise of the ethical will and solving the riddle of life, both of which are closely intertwined with the view of the world *sub specie aeterni*. According to Wittgenstein, viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* means viewing the world under the aspect of eternity. Eternity is understood not as infinite temporal duration, but as timelessness belonging to those who live in the present [TLP: 6.4311].⁷

⁶ Wittgenstein uses the word '*Anschauung*' in 6.45, which has been translated as 'contemplation' by Ogden and 'view' by Pears and McGuinness. I will favour the latter given that the implication of Wittgenstein's remarks suggests that by '*Anschauung*' he means an (active) perspective or way of seeing (see [Mulhall 2007: 238-239; Atkinson 2009: 68-69,74-75, 113] for a defence).

⁷ Wittgenstein is implicitly distinguishing between the 'present' as it is ordinarily understood, i.e., a certain instance within time that is found between the past and the future, from the 'present' associated to the view of the world *sub specie aeterni*, which he characterizes as the timelessness pertaining to eternity.

Adopting this view of the world, then, requires situating ourselves *outside* space and time through living in the present, i.e., in timelessness (cf. [TLP: 6.4312, 6.45]). In other words, only by living in timelessness can we, thereby, view the world *sub specie aeterni* from *outside* space and time. The usual way of looking at things sees objects *in* space and time from the midst of them. Conversely, the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* sees the world *together* with space and time from outside [NB: 7.10.16].

Contrary to the attitude discussed in section 2.1, the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* is *outside* space and time. It is not a happening *in* the world that can be meaningfully described with senseful propositions. We can describe what is in our visual field, but we cannot describe the eye or the shape of our visual field (cf. [TLP: 5.633-5.641]). On my proposed interpretation, then, the mark of the ethical is a metaphysical one, not a physical one –abiding, therefore, with Wittgenstein’s fact-value distinction.⁸

In the remainder of this section, I argue that the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* is constitutive of the good exercise of the ethical will, the solution to the riddle of life and, by extension, the good ethical life. Against those interpreters who characterize the correct ethical attitude as a mental state, I offer a proposal that avoids the paradoxical appeal to ethical mental states. Against those who do not characterize the correct ethical attitude as a mental state, I offer a proposal with better textual evidence that avoids some of the confusions that stem from invoking the notion ‘attitude’.

3.1. The ethical will

According to Wittgenstein, ethics is concerned with being ethically good, receiving ethical reward (i.e., happiness) and living a good, meaningful and ethical life. However, as a consequence of the fact-value distinction, ethical actions are not to be understood as mental (e.g., attitudes) or physical actions that occur *in* the world.

Many Wittgenstein scholars (e.g. [Rudebush and Berg 1979: 152-153; Cavalier 1980; Diamond 2000: 154, 166-168; Kremmer 2001, 58; Mulhall 2007: 232-233, 236,

⁸ The ethical self that views the world *sub specie aeterni* must be situated *outside* space and time. Namely, the ethical self cannot be a part of the world. It must be a limit of the world (like ethics). Here I will endorse the interpretation offered by Fairhurst [2019] (cf. [TLP: 5.632-5.641]; see Appelqvist [2013, 48] and Kuusela [2018, 45] for similar pronouncements), according to which the ethical subject is conceived as the metaphysical subject discussed in the 5.6s of the *Tractatus*. Contrary the human being, the metaphysical subject does not belong to the world. It resides *outside* space and time. It is this metaphysical subject that is the ethical subject, the bearer of the ethical.

243-245; Hughes 2009: 52; Tejedor 2013: 63, 73-79; Harchourt Forthcoming: 1-5, 8-9]) fail to spell out the consequences of Wittgenstein's fact-value distinction and, therefore, have wrongly assumed that Wittgenstein's ethics has implications for our actions and conduct *in* the world. The clearest example is to be found in the work of Rudebush and Berg, Mulhall, Tejedor and Harchourt, who claim that being ethically good amounts to a 'disposition to use signs in a way that demonstrates one's conceptual clarity' [Tejedor 2013, 55]. This reading goes against Wittgenstein's fact-value distinction, since the mark of ethical goodness (i.e., conceptual clarity) and the mark of ethical badness (conceptual confusion) are both understood as physical marks in the world. Against 6.41 and 6.4321, certain states of affairs, for instance the utterance of a senseful proposition, are regarded as ethically valuable and the solution to ethical problems.

Following Wittgenstein's discussion on the topic of ethical punishment and ethical reward, Wittgenstein focuses on the will in 6.423 and 6.43. There he distinguishes between the *phenomenal* will and the *ethical* will.⁹ The phenomenal will is conceived as a certain wish or desire (i.e. a mental state) that is of interest only to psychology and not ethics, insofar as it is a fact that cannot be the mark of the ethical.

The ethical will, meanwhile, is the subject of ethical attributes and the main ethical action of Wittgenstein's ethics in the *Tractatus*. Contrary to the *phenomenal* will, the ethical will does not have a physical mark in the world –hence why 'it is impossible to speak about' it [TLP: 6.43]. The ethical will deals with the world as a limited whole *together* with space and time, instead of encountering objects *in* space and time from the midst of them –as is the case with the phenomenal will. Thus, instead of altering facts in the world, the good and bad exercise of the ethical will alters the limits of the world, making it wax and wane as a whole, so that it becomes altogether different. But what is the good and bad exercise of the will? In what way does it alter the limits of the world? And how does it allow us to achieve ethical reward (i.e., ethical happiness) and, thereby, live a good ethical life?

Ordinarily, we express preference for certain facts over others and we attempt to

⁹ Wittgenstein [Waismann 1979: 92-93], in his meetings with the Vienna Circle, offers a similar distinction to explain the double meaning of ethical expressions (e.g., will, good, bad, *etcetera*). He distinguishes between their psychological sense, e.g. 'He is a good tennis player', and their non-psychological or ethical sense –a distinction used in the *Tractatus* (cf. [TLP: 5.641]) to differentiate the human being from the metaphysical subject. Wittgenstein [LOE: 5] later reformulated this distinction in terms of relative value/sense and absolute value/sense.

alter the happenings in the world in order to attain those facts we regard as valuable. The problem arises when fate does not unfold as we had wished or desired and we are left feeling unhappy. How can we overcome this predicament? How can we control fate and alter the world in order to achieve happiness and avoid unhappiness? The solution to this predicament is not to be found in a certain physical or mental action. Conversely, it is to be found in the good exercise of the ethical will.

The good exercise of the ethical will demands viewing the world *sub specie aeterni*. In viewing the world under the aspect of eternity we are able to feel the world as a limited whole and alter its limits [TLP: 6.45]. On the one hand, from this view we see that ‘no part of the world is privileged or preferred to another’ [Hughes 2009: 57]. In other words: through viewing the world *sub specie aeterni*, we are able to feel the world as a whole and see that no part of the world is more ethically valuable than another. The occurrence of one fact instead of another is ethically irrelevant because ethical value does not lie *in* the world [TLP: 6.4-6.421].

On the other hand, in adopting the standpoint of eternity and seeing the world as a limited whole we are able to see the connection between the phenomenal will and the world and its ethical implications. Wittgenstein ([TLP: 6.373-6.374] cf. [TLP: 2.061-2.062]) explains that there is no causal or logical necessitating relation between the phenomenal will and the world: the world is independent of the will.¹⁰ Hughes [2009: 56-57] takes Wittgenstein as suggesting that the phenomenal will *cannot* change the world. However, this interpretation is misguided.

Rejecting a necessitating relation (i.e., a logical relation) between the phenomenal will and the happenings that constitute its fulfilment does not encompass the claim that it is impossible for our will to alter the world. ‘Just as the only necessity that exists is *logical* necessity, so too the only impossibility that exists is *logical* impossibility’ [TLP: 6.375]. Wittgenstein’s point is that we can assign probabilities to the fulfilment of our will, but there is no certainty or indubitability that these happenings will occur [Teichmann 2015: 50]. Namely, we cannot alter these probabilities. We cannot will the relation between our will and the happenings that constitute its fulfilment. Whatever we may wish for only happens by grace of fate.

¹⁰ In 6.373-6.374 Wittgenstein discusses the *phenomenal* will, not the *ethical* will. Overlooking this difference can contribute to an inadequate exegesis of Wittgenstein’s ethics, as is the case for Kelly [1995: 572] and Morris [2008: 323-324].

Viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* allows us to situate ourselves *outside* space and time (cf. [TLP: 6.4312, 6.45]) and solve the predicament posed above. Regardless of how fate may unfold and whether it coincides with our phenomenal will or not, we are able to live in harmony with the world by seeing it *sub specie aeterni* and, therefore, recognizing that there is no value in the world nor a logical necessitating relation between the phenomenal will and the world (cf. [NB 30.7.16]). In viewing the world correctly and living in harmony with whatever the outcome of fate may be, we alter the limits of the world so it ceases to be the origin of ethical conflict, frustration and unhappiness, and becomes an unconditionally happy world. Namely, whatever we decide to do, there is no reason for us to be ethically distraught if the world does not accord to our wishes and desires, given that whatever happens in the world is valueless and out of our necessary control.¹¹ (I believe this exemplifies how facts ‘contribute only to setting the [ethical] problem, not to its solution’ [TLP: 6.4321]. ‘The facts do not belong to the performance of the ethical task [...] because that task is precisely to apprehend and accept the facts as facts’ [Mulhall 2007, 238].)

“Whoever realizes this will not want to give his body or the human body a preferred place in the world” [NB 9.11.16]. No part of the world is privileged over another. There is no need to live at war with the world in order to bend its happenings and achieve happiness. Ethical happiness is not found in our ability to control fate and necessitate the occurrence of certain valueless facts. Conversely, it is found in the good exercise of the ethical will. Namely, living in ethical harmony with the world by viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* and altering its limits to make it an unconditionally happy world –without the need to effect any change *in* the world (cf. [TLP: 6.43]). Our life, then, becomes a happy life –since the world and life are one (cf. [TLP: 5.621]).

Meanwhile, the bad exercise of the ethical will involves an inability to view the world *sub specie aeterni* and situate ourselves *outside* space and time (cf. [TLP: 6.4312, 6.45]).¹² We look for ethical happiness in the occurrence of certain facts, which we regard

¹¹ See [Hacker 1986; Morris 2008; Tejedor 2013; Fairhurst 2019] for a discussion on the parallelisms between Wittgenstein’s and Schopenhauer’s ethics. Relatedly, Wittgenstein’s work is also reminiscent of Spinoza’s ethics, from whom he takes the notion *sub specie aeterni* (Churchill [2009] is one of the few interpreters that acknowledges this connection).

¹² Wittgenstein, in his *Notebooks*, offered a similar distinction between our usual way of looking at things and the view *sub specie aeterni*. ‘The usual way of looking at things sees objects as it were from the midst of them, and the view *sub specie aeternitatis* from outside’ [NB: 7.10.16]. Despite the variations in his

as ethically valuable. When fate does not accord to our plans, we are unable to live in ethical harmony with the world and we set out to change it in order to satisfy our wishes and desires, and attain those facts we perceive as valuable –thus living at war with the world.

The issue here is neither that reality does not obey our phenomenal will nor our readiness and eagerness to act and change the world, since these are just valueless facts. Rather it is our inability to live in harmony with the world as a consequence of not seeing it *sub specie aeterni* and, therefore, failing to recognize that there is no value in the world and that there is no logical necessitating relation between the phenomenal will and the world. In viewing the world incorrectly, we develop a false sense of ethical responsibility¹³ for the occurrence of certain facts instead of others and, consequently, we face ethical punishment: the world becomes an unhappy world and our life becomes an unhappy life.

Our unhappiness, then, is not a consequence of reality not obeying our will, but rather of *our* inability to view the world correctly. As Wittgenstein explains in his private correspondence:

If I am unhappy and know that my unhappiness reflects a gross discrepancy between myself and life as it is, I have solved nothing... so long as I have not achieved the supreme and crucial insight that that discrepancy is not the fault of life as it is, but of myself as I am. [Engelmann 1967: 76-77]

3.2. Misconceptions about the ethical will

Hughes' [2009: 56-57] misguided exegetical claims about the phenomenal will in 6.373-6.374 lead an inadequate interpretation of Wittgenstein's ethical will. He suggests that

wording, the general idea seems to be shared in both works. Wittgenstein also alludes to a similar distinction when he explains 'that the scientific way of looking at a fact is not the way to look at it as a miracle' [LOE: 11].

¹³ I am not claiming that people are not responsible for their own actions. If someone kills a human being we *should* ('should' is used here as legal should, not an *ethical* should) legally prosecute them and hold them accountable for what they have done. My point is that, for Wittgenstein, there is no ethical responsibility here because we are dealing with valueless facts -which seemingly coincides with Wittgenstein's reported inhumane point of view when hearing shocking stories [Richter 2002, 327-328]. This can raise questions regarding the ethical status of Wittgenstein's ethics, as it neither prescribes nor proscribes actions in the world. Nevertheless, dealing with this issue in detail exceeds the scope of the present paper.

the good exercise of the ethical will involves accepting that we *cannot* change the world and that we only become involved in unhappiness when we wish things were otherwise.¹⁴ Likewise other interpreters, such as Worthington [1981: 483], Thomas [1999: 197] and Richter [2002: 335], claim that the good exercise of the ethical will requires us to renounce influence on the world –we must accept that we *cannot* change the world.

However, the good exercise of the ethical will cannot show itself in the world through the subject’s renunciation to act. Letting the world run its course or, conversely, interfering with the happenings of the world is neither ethically good nor ethically bad. Both our renunciation to act and our eagerness to act are facts that occur in the world and, thereby, are ethically valueless.¹⁵ Living in harmony with the world does not entail (or require) acting in a certain way or renouncing to act.

The good exercise of the ethical will amounts to seeing that facts, which are seen *together* with space and time (not *in* space and time), are valueless and, on the other hand, ‘that whatever the one does, reality does not obey one’s will, and that one must accept the outcome, whatever it may be’ [Kuusela 2018: 49].¹⁶ There is no problem in physically and mentally acting in a certain way as long as we are able to live in harmony with the world by viewing it correctly. Against Richter [2002: 335], there is no contradiction between Wittgenstein’s ethics and his non-stoic way of living (e.g., his involvement in the First World War). Living in harmony with whatever fate may bring does not entail a

¹⁴ In section 3.1 I opted in favour of speaking about living in harmony with the world, instead of speaking about acceptance. The reason for this decision is twofold. First, Wittgenstein never spoke about the idea of ‘acceptance’ in any of his early work on ethics. Meanwhile, we do find some textual evidence supporting the idea of a harmonious life in the *Notebooks* (cf. [NB 30.7.16]). Second, speaking about acceptance may lead to some of the issues described in section 2, insofar as it can be understood as a certain attitude (i.e., a mental state or a state of mind) that can be described with senseful propositions.

¹⁵ Furthermore, physical and mental actions are motivated by accidental purposes and motives contingent on personal inclinations (cf. [LOE: 6-7]). Only ethical actions (e.g., the good and bad exercise of the ethical will), which are not facts in the world, are motivated by genuine ethical value.

¹⁶ Kuusela’s arguments to support this claim differ from the ones I have offered. He rejects the idea of renunciation on the basis that not phenomenally willing anything at all is morally questionable ‘insofar as it may lead, for example, to a passive acceptance of injustices’ [Kuusela 2018: 49]. I believe this argument is problematic as it runs against Wittgenstein’s fact-value distinction. It suggests that one must phenomenally will such-and-such in order to be ethically good. Hence, the mark of ethical goodness and ethical badness is physical mark. Certain facts (e.g., phenomenally willing something) are deemed more ethically valuable than others (e.g., not phenomenally willing anything).

renunciation to act. The ethical will *only* alters the limits of the world, not the *facts* [TLP: 6.43].

This inadequate interpretation of the ethical will points to a deeper issue in the exegesis of Wittgenstein's *Tractarian* ethics. Many Wittgenstein scholars (e.g., [McGuinness 2002: 157; Richter 2002: 335; Morris 2008: 328]) take the good and bad exercise of the ethical will as involving a certain change *in* the world. For instance, McGuinness [2002, 157] explains that, according to Wittgenstein, the good exercise of the ethical will does not allow a man to promote his own ethical happiness at the cost of another's life. However, Wittgenstein's remarks do not warrant such conclusion. The good and bad exercise of the ethical will cannot alter the facts *in* the world [TLP: 6.43]. These interpreters fail to spell out the consequences of Wittgenstein's fact-value distinction and, therefore, wrongly assume that Wittgenstein's ethics has implications for our actions and conduct *in* the world.

Another example is found in the work of Cavalier [1980: 159-160, 165-166, 173-175, 184, 187-195], Edwards [1982: 26, 46-47, 57, 67-68], Churchill [2009: 113-114, 121-123], Hughes [2009: 52, 56-58, 60] and Appelqvist [2013: 47-49, 51, 53]. As explained in 2.1, they defend that the correct ethical attitude is living in acceptance and agreement with the world by adopting the alien will (i.e., God's will) on which we appear dependent.

Leaving aside the fact that Wittgenstein does not mention nor discuss God's will (see note 20) in the *Tractatus*, this interpretation contradicts Wittgenstein's fact-value distinction. It mistakenly claims that certain facts, such as aligning our phenomenal will with the alien will on which we appear dependent, are more valuable than others, such as failing to do so. The mark of ethical goodness and ethical badness is mistakenly conceived as a physical mark in the world.

Furthermore, this interpretation fails to abide by Wittgenstein's distinction between the phenomenal will and the ethical will. On the one hand, it mistakenly suggests that the good exercise of the ethical will demands a certain change in the phenomenal will—despite it being of interest only to psychology, and not ethics. On the other hand, it fails to realize that the ethical will can only alter the limits of the world, not the facts [TLP: 6.43].

3.3. The meaning of life

Having examined Wittgenstein's understanding of the ethical will, we can now explore the problem of the meaning of life and how its solution contributes to living a good ethical life.¹⁷ According to a common view (e.g., [Cavalier 1980: 199; Mulhall 2007: 240-24; Morris 2008; 328-329]), we are able to live meaningful life by dissolving the problem of life and, thereby, simply living life itself.

This common view mainly relies on Wittgenstein's discussion of the problem of life and its solution in propositions 6.5-6.522. There he explains that if an answer cannot be put into words, neither can the question and, therefore, the problem ceases to exist (cf. [TLP: 6.5, 6.521]). The problem is a pseudo-problem. Thus, a meaningful life is one that is not troubled or tormented by this pseudo-problem and does not view life as ethically problematic.

I believe it is mistaken to claim that a meaningful life amounts to dissolving the problem of life and, thereby, simply living life itself. On the one hand, the vanishing of the problem of life cannot be the sole requirement for a meaningful life. If this were the case, it would be possible to live a meaningful life despite having an incorrect ethical view of the world, a bad exercise of the ethical will and being ethically unhappy, as long as we made the problem vanish. This conclusion seems unacceptable.

On the other hand, there is no evidence in the 6.5s to substantiate the claim made by this common view. In the 6.5s Wittgenstein presents a method to (dis)solve pseudo-problems (cf. [TLP: 6.5]) and then sets out to exemplify how this method can be applied to tackle various philosophical problems. In 6.51 he focuses on the problem of scepticism, in 6.52 he focuses on the problem of life –understood as a philosophical problem (cf. [Christensen 2011: 799-800])– and, finally, in 6.53 he focuses on philosophical and metaphysical problems in general, prompting him to describe the only strictly correct method of philosophy.

Wittgenstein's explanation of the (dis)solution of the problem of life in 6.52-6.522 teaches us that this problem and its solution cannot be expressed in meaningful propositions. In other words, contrary to what philosophers had previously believed, philosophy cannot meaningfully speak about this problem and its solution. Conversely, it can only demonstrate that, whenever someone wanted to say something philosophical about this problem and its solution, they fail to give meaning to certain signs in their propositions and, therefore, are speaking nonsense (cf. [TLP: 6.53]).

¹⁷ It should be noted that Wittgenstein uses the notions 'value', 'sense' and 'meaning' indistinctly in ethics.

This clarification, unfortunately, tells us nothing about the meaning of life and the world nor the difference between living a meaningful life and living a meaningless life. Wittgenstein philosophical clarification of the problem of life in the 6.52s is no more than a consequence of the fact-value distinction outlined in the 6.4s and his understanding of pictures (i.e., propositions and thoughts). It should not be taken as Wittgenstein's final say on the meaning of life.

It may be countered that there is no such thing as the meaning of life and that, consequently, the (dis)solution of the problem of life allows us to live a life free from the torment that arises from this ethical pseudo-problem. However, this directly conflicts with Wittgenstein's remarks in 6.522 and 6.41. He explains that 'there are, indeed, things that cannot be put into words. They *make themselves manifest*. They are what is mystical' [TLP: 6.522]. The meaning of life, then, is not to be found in the dis(solution) of a certain pseudo-problem. Conversely, 'the sense of the world must lie outside of the world' [TLP: 6.41], in the mystical –like ethics. The point of Wittgenstein's dis(solution) of the problem of life is to help us avoid searching for the meaning of life in the world and direct us to the mystical, as it is there where we will find the meaning of life (see [Atkinson 2009] for a study of the mystical).

In 6.41 and 6.4312 Wittgenstein explains that immortality is often introduced in hopes of solving the riddle of life. Wittgenstein contends, however, that even if there was a guarantee of the temporal immortality of the human soul, our eternal survival after death does not provide a solution to the riddle. Conversely, it just makes the riddle eternal. 'The solution of the riddle of life in space and time lies *outside* space and time' [TLP: 6.4312]. Namely, 'the sense of the world must lie outside of the world' [TLP: 6.41] –the meaning of life and the world are one and the same, since 'the world and life are one' [TLP: 5.621].

Thomas [1999: 196-197] and Worthington [1981: 486] discuss these propositions in relation to NB 6.7.16. They claim that we overcome the problem of life by living in eternity and, thereby, renouncing influence on the world by adopting the alien will on which we appear dependent. However, this interpretation is inadequate in so far as it claims that the mark of ethical goodness is a physical mark in the world (see sections 2.1 and 3.2). Furthermore, against 6.4312 and 6.52-6.522, Thomas and Worthington claim that the solution to the riddle of life lies *in* space and time. Specifically, it lies in our ability to renounce influence on the world and align our phenomenal will with the alien will on which we appear dependent.

The meaning of life and the world, on the contrary, is to be found in the *mystical* view that allows us to see the world from *outside* space and time as something meaningful: the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* (cf. [TLP: 6.4312, 6.45]).¹⁸ Viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* from *outside* space and time allows us to see that there is no value *in* the world (cf. [TLP: 6.41, 6.4312, 6.52-6.522]). Thus, there is no point in endlessly searching for the meaning of life and the world in valueless and accidental facts. Conversely, we must alter the limits of the world to make it altogether different, without effecting any change *in* the world.

As explained in section 3.1, viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* alters the limits of the world so it ceases to be the source of ethical conflict and becomes an unconditionally happy world. In doing so, we are able to recognize that it is this unconditionally happy world as a *whole* that is meaningful and valuable, not a particular instance of it (e.g., the occurrence of one fact instead of another). ‘It is not *how* things are in the world that is mystical, but *that* it exists’ [TLP 6.44].

Regardless of what may happen *in* the world, the world and life as a whole remain unconditionally happy and, by extension, valuable and meaningful when seen correctly (i.e., *sub specie aeterni*).¹⁹ In other words, giving sense and meaning to our life (and the world) is accomplished through a good exercise of the ethical will and, in consequence, seeing the world *sub specie aeterni*, as a limited whole, as something valuable and meaningful –without altering the facts *in* the world. A happy world is an ethically and valuable world and a happy life is an ethically meaningful and valuable life: a good ethical life.

¹⁸ Appelqvist [2013, 206-207] discusses this idea in relation to religion and God. She explains that it is through a mystical experience that we are able live in harmony with reality and solve the problem of life. This experience is not only ethical but also religious: it involves a belief in God (cf. [NB: 11.6.16, 8.7.16]). ‘To believe in God is to see one’s life as meaningful in spite of its factual meaninglessness’ [Appelqvist 2013, 206]. Unfortunately, there is insufficient evidence in the *Tractatus* to claim that God plays a primordial role in Wittgenstein’s ethics the good ethical life (see note 20).

¹⁹ This mystical view of the world *outside* space and time may allow us to explain the connection between ethics and aesthetics in 6.421. It could be argued that the view of the world *sub specie aeterni* transforms the limits of the world so it becomes both an ethically and aesthetically meaningful and valuable world. Wittgenstein explains something along these lines in the *Notebooks* when he claims that ‘the work of art is the object seen *sub specie aeternitatis*; and the good life is the world seen *sub specie aeternitatis*. This is the connexion between art and ethics’ [NB: 7.10.16]. Notwithstanding, examining this issue in detail exceeds the scope of this paper and requires a separate investigation.

Meanwhile, the bad exercise of the ethical will leads to an unhappy world and an unhappy life because of our inability to see the world *sub specie aeterni* and alter its limits correctly. As a consequence of not viewing the world as a whole from *outside* space and time, we are unable to see that there is no value *in* the world (cf. [TLP: 6.41, 6.4312, 6.52-6.522]). Thus, we endlessly search for the meaning of life and the world in accidental, valueless and meaningless facts, but to no avail. This pointless search for the meaning of life and the world *in* space and time leads to a life at war with the world (see section 3.1). The world and life, therefore, become altogether unhappy and, by extension, meaningless and valueless, without effecting any change *in* the world. We are unable to live a good ethical life because of not viewing the world correctly.

4. A good ethical life

Summarizing, the good ethical life is predicated on a good exercise of the ethical will and solving the riddle of life, both of which demand viewing the world *sub specie aeterni* in order to make the world (and life) a happy, meaningful and valuable world (and life). Meanwhile, the bad ethical life is predicated on a bad exercise of the ethical will and an inability to solve the riddle of life as a consequence of not viewing the *sub specie aeterni*, thus leading to a unhappy, meaningless and valueless world and life.

The difference between the good ethical life and a bad ethical life is not to be found in the facts *in* the world, but rather in our ability or inability to have a correct ethical view of the world and alter the limits of the world to make it altogether different. For instance, two individuals could live the same life, have the same mental states and face exactly the same happenings, and act in the same way throughout their life. However, as a consequence of having either the correct or incorrect ethical view of the world, one of them sees the world as a happy one and the other as an unhappy one.

The lack of a physical mark in the world to distinguish between the good ethical life and the bad ethical life means that we are unable to recognize if other ethical subjects have a correct ethical view of the world and *viceversa* –i.e., they are unable to recognize if we have a correct ethical view of the world. Furthermore, the ethical reward and ethical punishment that is internal to ethical actions also lacks a physical mark in the world. Ethical happiness and ethical unhappiness are not describable psychological or mental states. Hence why it is the world and life as a whole that is happy or unhappy, and not a particular instance of it (cf. [TLP: 6.43]).

However, given that the good ethical life does not result in physical reward (e.g.,

feeling happiness or joy) nor is it externally recognizable, what is the point of being ethically good and living a good ethical life? First, being recognized by others as ethically good or bad is unimportant for Wittgenstein. Ethics is a matter of personal ethical responsibility. There is no room for external recognition or validation.

Second, physical reward and physical punishment are accidental facts in the world that are dependent on fate. There is no ethical reason in favour of striving for facts that are valueless, beyond our control and could have easily been otherwise.

Finally, and most importantly, there is no rational justification or explanation regarding why we should be ethically good and live a good ethical life –and if there were we could not put it into words, given that propositions ‘can express nothing that is higher’ ([TLP: 6.42]).²⁰ The reasons in favour of being ethically good and living a good ethical life are to be ethically good and live a good ethical life. The value of being ethically good and living a good ethical life is self-evident: it admits no justification or explanation (cf. [TLP: 6.4, 6.41]). As Wittgenstein later explained: being ethically good is the absolute right road, ‘the road which everybody on seeing it would, with logical necessity, have to go, or be ashamed for not going’ [LOE: 7].

²⁰ Wittgenstein makes a similar point when discussing theological ethics with Schlick. According to Schlick there ‘used to be two conceptions of the essence of the good: according to the shallower interpretation the good is good because it is what God wants; according to the profounder interpretation God wants the good because it is good’ [Waismann 1979: 115]. Wittgenstein countered that it is actually the first interpretation that is profounder since ‘it cuts off the way to any explanation ‘why’ it is good [...]’. The first conception says clearly that the essence of the good has nothing to do with facts and hence cannot be explained by any proposition’ [Waismann 1979, 115]. Throughout this discussion, Wittgenstein endorses his earlier remarks from the *Notebooks* regarding God and ethics. He explains that ‘if there is any proposition expressing precisely what I think, it is the proposition “What God commands, that is good”’ ([Waismann 1979, 115] cf. [Waismann 1979, 118]) –he offers a similar remark in *Culture and Value*: ‘what is Good is Divine too. That, strangely enough, sums up my ethics’ [CV 4/MS 107 192 c: 10.11.1929]. Lovibond, Hughes, Churchill, Richter and Appelqvist resorted to the *Notebooks* to explain the connection between God and ethics in the *Tractatus*. However, despite his earlier and later remarks on the connection between God and ethics, Wittgenstein explicitly avoided employing these remarks in the *Tractatus*, thus suggesting that the connection between God and ethics is no longer endorsed in these works. At most we find a reference to God in the *Prototractatus*, where Wittgenstein initially included the following remark to proposition 6.4412: ‘Wie sich alles verhält, ist Gott. Gott ist, wie sich alles verhält’ [MS 104, 84]. However, it leaves out the connection between God and ethics. Further arguments are required to substantiate the claim that Wittgenstein maintains this connection between God and ethics in the *Tractatus*.

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